

The Impact of Individuals Holding Multiple Jobs on Graduate Unemployment in South Africa

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The paper aims to investigate the impact of individuals holding multiple jobs on graduate unemployment in South Africa. The objective of this paper is to investigate the impact of individuals holding multiple jobs on graduate unemployment in South Africa. The research question that this paper seeks to answer from the research objective is: How do individuals holding multiple jobs affect graduate unemployment in South Africa? It argues that the high graduate unemployment rate in South Africa is perpetuated by individuals occupying multiple job positions. For example, most councillors elected to local government are also employed as teachers, and they are also serving in other community structures. While some are at home facing unemployment, others are busily juggling multiple job positions. This paper utilised "*Bana Ba Motho Ba Nwagathelana Hlogwana Ya Tsie*" proverb as a lens to tackle this unavoidable issue. In terms of methodology, this paper is qualitatively oriented and conducts a critical analysis of secondary data collected from peer-reviewed journals and dissertations. The findings of the paper reveal that a high rate of graduate unemployment is caused by individuals holding multiple jobs in South Africa. To confirm these findings, the paper delves into the reasons behind how people occupying multiple job positions cause a high graduate unemployment rate in South Africa. The paper recommends that there is a need to establish a legal framework that limits the number of jobs an individual can hold in South Africa.

Keywords: Job positions, graduate unemployment, proverb, South Africa

High unemployment continues to characterize South Africa (Molobela, 2023; Adejugbe, 2024). In the first quarter of 2024, unemployment in South Africa reached 32,9% (Adejugbe, 2024). In view of Buthelezi, Nxumalo, and Ngema (2024), the continued increment of unemployment in the country is caused by a focus on the requirement of 5 years or more experience in the public and private sector. Necessarily because many less educated, less experienced or qualified individuals are left out of the market. This perpetuates the unstoppable unemployment in South Africa. Molobela (2023) postulates that unemployment in South Africa affects both graduates and non-graduates, particularly between the ages of 18-34. This exists even though the efforts to create job opportunities. The reason why this exists is due to the fact that sharing of employment opportunities remains uneven, with many positions being filled by the same people, and these people can easily be replaced by other graduates or non-graduates (Nkuna, 2013). Thus, South Africa is faced with educated youth who are unemployed.

Molobela (2023: 108) did not hesitate to proclaim that "higher education and training institutions aim to produce graduates that can think beyond their qualifications and create multiple jobs." Meanwhile, graduate who penetrates the job market do not generate

employment opportunities but instead they occupy two or more job positions. Nkuna (2013) in his thesis discovered that occupying multiple roles in the local government not only reduces the available job vacancies but also produces insufficient management. These untouched issues of holding multiple jobs in South Africa have been fashioned by those who are fortunate to secure two or more employment opportunities. This paper argues that holding multiple jobs can be seen as personal gain, but it comes at the expense of others who are unemployed.

This paper calls for the need for legislative framework that can produce a more inclusive approach to employment and make sure that opportunities reach people who are left out of the job market. In order to support the claims of this paper, the authors commence by outlining the methodology and the proverb as the focus lens for this paper. It then delves into the conceptualisation of individuals holding multiple jobs in South Africa, discusses the meaning of graduate unemployment in the country, examines the impact of multiple job occupancy on graduate unemployment, and discusses the challenges posed by individuals holding multiple jobs in South Africa.

Method

This paper followed a qualitative research approach. In its data collection, desktop research was conducted to gather secondary data on the impact of individuals holding multiple jobs on graduates' unemployment in South Africa. It gathered data from peer-reviewed journal articles and dissertations. The inclusion and exclusion criteria for articles provided in Table 1 were applied in this article, which examines the impact of individuals holding multiple jobs on graduates' unemployment in South Africa. Data was also collected from scientific databases and sources, including Google Scholar and University libraries.

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Table 1*Research Publications Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria*

Criteria	Inclusion	Exclusion
Date of publication	Articles published from 1999 to 2024, which enable rich data collection on research problem and topic.	Articles published before 1999 and articles not addressing the research problem and topic.
Article type	Peer-reviewed articles and dissertations.	Unpublished articles and dissertations.
Languages	English articles	Other languages articles
Article Relevance	Article that addresses research topic in question.	Article not relevant to the research topic in question.
Sample Number of Publications	The paper considered seventy (n=70) publications as the target sample, but only twenty-seven (n=27) were included in this paper because they were more relevant.	Forty-three (43) were not included as they were not addressing the research problem and topic.

Analysis of the Paper

These authors undertake this paper, looking closely at the cells of thematic analysis. Nkoana (2025) in his master's dissertation he mentions that thematic analysis is a qualitative data analysis that can be used to find and interpret recurring patterns within data. Authors choose this type of analysis to assist in making sense of large amounts of written information by grouping related content into themes that capture important meanings or shared experiences.

“Bana Ba Motho Ba Nwathelana Hlogwana Ya Tsie”

“Bana Ba Motho Ba Nwathelana Hlogwana ya Tsie” is a Sepedi proverb that conveys the idea that all children in a household should share the head of a locust to ensure that everyone has something to eat (Kganyago, 2008). This proverb offers valuable insight into the importance of sharing wealth and resources within households or a country among its citizens. The proverb's underlying belief that communal sharing is essential cannot be realised if one or a few individuals within a family or country seek to monopolise resources and enjoy the benefits alone. The greatest of our ancestors who engineered this proverb perceived the head of locust as a limited resource and if limited resources are not shared fairly and equally among the citizens in the country, majority of the local people would be subjected to a high level of poverty and inequality in the country. This means that comprehending and applying the principle behind this proverb is crucial and can never be outdated, and it should be considered not just at the family level but for South Africa as a whole.

“Bana Ba Motho Ba Nwathelana Hlogwana ya Tsie” as a lens guiding this paper informs that sharing opportunities (like sharing of the head of a locust) remain at the centre of addressing graduate unemployment in South Africa. Necessarily because this proverb maintains a view that individuals holding multiple job positions are effectively enjoying the head of the locust alone, whereas others who need employment are left with nothing to eat. Therefore, this serves as an eye-opener to the South African government to adopt this proverb in their recruitment legislation. This would ensure that employment opportunities are distributed fairly and equally among South African citizens. If the principle of this proverb is implemented, the issue of graduates' unemployment in South Africa could be significantly reduced.

Review of Literature

Conceptualisation of Individuals Holding Multiple Jobs in South Africa

Individuals holding multiple jobs refer to individuals who hold and

perform multiple jobs simultaneously (Campion, Caza, & Moss, 2020). This means that these individuals work in different roles or for different employers at the same time. For example, most councillors elected to local government are also employed as teachers, and they are also serving in other community structures. According to Campion et al. (2020), one of the primary reasons for people to hold multiple jobs is to diversify their income sources, which is particularly relevant in economies where wages are low or job security is uncertain. Additionally, some individuals may hold multiple jobs because they are underemployed in their primary job, working part-time or in a position that does not fully utilise their skills (Hall & Kudlyak, 2022). However, in some cases, professionals like teachers and lecturers, who are employed full-time, may seek additional job opportunities, such as job positions with the Independent Electoral Commission (IEC) in South Africa, which are often intended for unemployed youth. Effective time management is required to fulfil the duties of multiple jobs (Nkuna, 2013). This means that individuals who wish to occupy multiple jobs should first understand their personal timetable. Others may occupy multiple gain broader skills or pursue different interests. Therefore, balancing responsibilities and demands of two or more jobs cannot be ignored on holding multiple jobs. However, holding multiple jobs creates several problems for every country; thus, the following subsection unfolds the challenges faced by South Africa caused by individuals holding multiple jobs.

Conundrums Facing South Africa due to Individuals Holding Multiple Job Positions

People who occupy multiple jobs produce the following challenges, including perpetual high graduates' unemployment, high concentration of experience on one-person, inequitable distribution of resources, undermining of trust and inefficient management (Nkoana, Mmacheone, & Selelo, 2024a). This section starts by unpacking perpetual high unemployment as an issue.

Perpetual High Graduates' Unemployment: Campion et al. (2020) point out that fellow South African who hold numerous job positions reduces the available employment opportunities for others. This painful and cruel behaviour adds to the high employment rate in the country. This happens when fewer job openings are left for the unemployed are still occupied by those who already have employment. In South Africa, where job scarcity is a mushroom that overshadows almost all the graduates, holding multiple jobs should be dealt with immediately without hesitation.

High Concentration of Experience in One Person: Individuals occupying multiple job positions is a disaster that creates a high concentration of experience for one person (De Guzman & Choi, 2013). Necessarily, because these practices favor only a few people. This concurs with the sentiment made by Buthelezi et al. (2024) that individuals holding multiple jobs restrict others who are unemployed an opportunity from getting critical competencies. This crisis, in view of the author's delay others from building up their career. Thus, this action often leads to monopolization of certain careers by a single individual. Depending on such individuals by an organization cannot be ignored because when they are absent, organizations are more likely to struggle to make decisions and strategic plans. Furthermore, new leaders cannot emerge under this condition of concentrated expertise due to limited mentorship. The symptoms of this condition are often seen in a country where individuals still find it happy or good when they are the only ones who have a certain experience or skill. Hence, Haque, Nawaz, and Tariq (2021) proclaim that without establishing an inclusive legislative framework, most graduates are likely to be left out of the job market. This implies that the enforcement of such acts is only hoped to create an environment that enables the sharing of experience and expertise.

Inequitable Distribution of Resources: The greatest scholar in the view of authors, Molobela (2023) reminds us that holding multiple employment in South Africa establishes inequitable distribution of resources, including salaries, training opportunities and career advancement. This simply means that a few individuals at the start, middle or end of the month their bank become pregnant while others do not receive anything. Creation of dissatisfaction and disengagement among other people is then born because others who are not working believe that they are not given equal opportunities to attain their big dreams. Furthermore, the authors such as (RF) inform the authors of this paper through writing that in developing countries such as South Africa, unequal distribution of resources within the labour market is not a thing of the past but a contemporary challenge. Labour market inequalities are perpetuated by a high concentration of experience on one person because such individuals turn to earn higher salaries, receive more training and develop their career rapidly (Grimshaw, Fagan, Hebson, & Tavora, 2017).

Undermining of Trust: Trust remains some oxygen for effective governance; however, some practices, such as holding multiple jobs, continue to erode it. Governance credibility cannot be achieved due to the practice of people holding multiple jobs in the public sector. This is due to Nkoana et al. (2024a) who wrote about individuals who hold multiple jobs in local government that occupying multiple job opportunities create conflict of interest and destroys transparency. This creates a condition where local people including graduates longer have enormous trust in the South African government. Most people who notice this practice would synonymize it with favoritism, patronage, or an unfair decision-making process, which further undermines trust within the organization (Nkoana, Selelo, & Mashamaite, 2024b).

Kuipers, Higgs, Kickert, Tummers, Grandia, and Van der Voet (2014) state that holding multiple jobs reduces effective commitment among employees in both public and private sectors due to overlapping responsibilities. This happens when individuals have more duties to do and often neglect other duties because their due date might be close. Moreover, Nkoana et al. (2024a) highlight that holding multiple jobs can make an individual manage

conflicting mandates or report to different authorities, decision-making becomes fragmented, and strategic coherence suffers. Kuipers et al. (2014) agree that this practice creates delayed responses, policy contradictions, and diminished service delivery quality, further eroding public confidence.

Inefficient Management: Unproductive management is more prevalent in a condition where individuals manage multiple jobs concurrently (Nkoana et al., 2024a). Nkuna (2013) who has extensive knowledge on local governance, laments that it is difficult for officials in local government who hold multiple jobs because they are stretched across several responsibilities. He further highlights that most officials are unable to devote adequate time, attention and strategic oversight to each; in the end, it produces inefficient management. Mokoale (2022) informs that fragmented governance like the above-mentioned, results in poor decision-making, delayed responses and sluggish service quality. Alosani, Yusoff, and Al-Dhaafri (2019) in their study found that inefficient management result in ineffective strategic planning that gives birth to hindered organizational excellence and innovation.

Holding multiple job positions is associated with overload, which reduces satisfaction and turnover intentions (Khan, Khan, Khan, & Khan, 2020). This is also clearly seen where managers are tasked with multiple roles within one institution without adequate support, they experience decision fatigue that compromises their ability to respond effectively to the emerging needs of organization. In addition, Al-Dhaafri, Alosani and Yusoff (2016) point out that holding multiple jobs or roles results in lack of role and excessive multitasking. This implies that challenges such as communication flows and delayed operational feedback loops would be addressed in organizations that practice this condition. As a result, inefficient management continues to exist in most organizations where individuals holding multiple jobs or roles is practiced.

The Meaning of Graduate Unemployment in South Africa

Talking and writing about graduate unemployment cannot expire because it is a persistent challenge. As long as it exists and continues to rise in South Africa, unfolding its meaning remains important. Molobela (2023) defines graduate unemployment as a condition where people with a college or university higher certificates, diplomas, degrees, honours, master's and doctoral are unable to secure employment that is consistent with their qualifications or any job in general. It is vividly clear that the cause of graduate unemployment is associated with employers frequently choosing candidates with prior work experience, even for jobs at the entry level. Forgetting that everyone has a starting point where they initially created their experience and sharpened their skills. This planned behaviour acts as a great wall that blocks recent graduates who may possess the necessary qualifications but lack hands-on experience.

Authors such as Bernasek and Long (2021) inform us that the meaning of graduate unemployment cannot be fully unfolded if the repercussions, such as reduced lifetime earnings and issues of meeting student loan obligations are not touched and included in the discussion of graduate unemployment. The inability of graduates to earn good money or pay student loans would promote brain drain, where highly skilled and educated individuals leave South Africa to look for better prospects (Selelo, Mokoale, & Mnisi, 2023). According to Rashid and Islam (2020), graduates who are

unemployed feel frustrated, experience lack of hope and a decline in self-worth. Due to a lack of hope and a decline in self-worth among graduates make a situation where most graduates rely on family or government assistance and some might choose to engage in illicit or illegal activities. At the end, education, due to unemployed graduates, would be synonyms with or equivalent to poverty and struggle. Hence, considering education as a means to escape poverty would become a thing of the past. This implies that there is a need to find other solutions to reduce poverty.

The Impact of Individuals Holding Multiple Jobs on Graduate Unemployment in South Africa

Authors, when reviewing the literature realised that topic of individuals holding multiple job positions and its impact on graduates' unemployment around the world and in South Africa is quite limited. But through the limited literature, authors discovered the study by Campion et al. (2020) which argues that occupying multiple jobs by certain officials or individuals reduces available job opportunities, especially entry-level positions for graduates and non-graduates. This serves as a caution that unemployment rates will increase as time goes on if this practice is not well managed. Highly experienced individuals have more advantages over less experienced individuals, hence securing jobs over less experienced individuals is easy even through following good recruitment practice. As the highly qualified individuals continue to secure multiple jobs, Green and Henseke (2020) found that educated graduates sometimes find themselves working in positions that are not consistent with their qualifications or potential. As a result, there will be a waste of skills in this economy.

Molobela (2023) asserts that uncured presence of experienced individuals in multiple jobs decapitates the upward mobility of younger employees including graduates. This means that opportunities for graduates to advance within organisation are limited. Abomaye-Nimenibo and Samuel (2021) mention that holding multiple jobs is often linked with individuals who have power or with extensive networks. This power or extensive networks assists individuals to secure multiple jobs, whereas fresh graduates from universities and disadvantaged backgrounds struggle to enter the job market. This clearly means that opportunities are concentrated among a few individuals and new entrants such as graduates, are excluded from meaningful workforce participation.

South Africa continues to struggle with graduate unemployment despite fluctuations in the rate of absorption, which measures the percentage of employed working-age population ranging from 58.6% in 2015, declining to 47.3% and subsequently rising to 60% in 2025 (Stats SA, 2025). Therefore, this difference marked by 15.4% shows the broader economic cycles; however, it fails to capture the quality and stability of graduate employment. Literature suggests that lack of permanent employment opportunities, low wages, lack of work experience, and limited access to professional networks resorts graduates to hold multiple jobs (Campion et al., 2020; Vosko, 2025).

Mseleku (2022) notes that graduates face inconsistency in terms of qualifications and available jobs, which leads to some of them taking multiple part-time jobs to sustain their income and post-internship graduate. According to Bhorat and Hodge (1999), state that multiple job holding in the South African labour market may be a result of underemployment, specifically among younger and educated individuals rather than an issue of economic resilience.

Graham and Mlatsheni (2015) further argue that structural barriers such as lack of experience and limited access to networks, worsen graduate unemployment, leading individuals into risky employment settings. Therefore, this finding indicates that graduates holding several jobs relying on informal or part-time work to support themselves, points out the issue of underemployment and lower economic activity. Moreover, the findings stress the need for policy interventions to address job quality and alignment with graduate skills rather than mere employment quantity.

Figure 1

Presenting Data Difference from Q4: 2024 and Q1: 2025

Note. Author: Stats SA (2025)

According to Stats SA (2025), labour stats show a disturbing increase in economic inactivity and unemployment, which indicates that the increasing momentum of people occupying several jobs may be worsening graduate unemployment. Stats SA (2025) indicated that employment reduced by 291,000 from 17,1 M to 16.6 M, meanwhile unemployment increased by 237,000 outstretching to 8.2 M and discouraged job seekers stayed static at 3.5 M. In addition, other not economically active (NEA) individuals rose by 177,000 (Stats SA, 2025). As a result, this transition shows a decline in the labour force, with fewer individuals working and many sliding into unemployment. Therefore, the increase in NEA figures recommends increasing disconnection from the labour market, specifically amongst young graduates.

Stats SA (2025) data shows increasing unemployment and NEA individuals, which aligns with the literature's concern about the labour market and informal jobs absorption limiting new entrants into the labour market. In addition, unemployment continues to be a problem in South Africa, where youth unemployment is over 40% despite rising tertiary enrollment (Stats SA, 2025). The rational income security through multiple jobs distorts the labour market; as a result, employers may overlook the shortage of labour while graduates continue to struggle to find employment opportunities. Moreover, the untracked increase in the informal employment sector may disguise the extent of underemployment. Stats SA (2025) reveals a declining labour market with academic research suggesting that multiple job holding is a necessary coping mechanism; however, it worsens the graduate unemployment. Therefore, a coordinated policy action is needed to correct the uneven distribution of employment opportunities to ensure that South African youth are not excluded from the economy.

Graduate Unemployment and Several Job Occupations

According to De Jongh, Mncayi-Makhanya, and Mdluli-Maziya (2024), state that alumni face conflict between their qualifications labour market absorption rate, thus leading to job banking and underemployment, where people take several low-skill jobs to make

a living. Duvisa (2019) states that employment hoarding by experienced workers who are occupying several positions can reduce first-level opportunities for new alumni, specifically in sectors such as public services, retail and education. Therefore, this change obstructs graduates' wrestle to get into the labour market; meanwhile, more experienced employees occupy available roles, often out of financial need.

Findings and Discussion

This paper adopted a qualitative research approach. This means that it reviews existing literature about individuals holding multiple jobs and their impact on graduates' unemployment in South Africa to attain its objectives and aims. This paper perceives that individuals holding multiple jobs contribute to graduate unemployment in South Africa. Highly qualified and experienced candidates preferred by employers are pushed to the sidelines of many young graduates from the job market, and promote unemployment issues. This paper further notes that the continued graduates' unemployment is likely to make qualifications synonymous or equivalent to poverty and struggle as opposed to a tool that can help the poor of the poorest to escape poverty and struggle. The paper also discovered that individuals holding multiple jobs can be driven by the need to diversify income or due to underemployment.

However, this practice is against the principle of “*Bana Ba Motho Ba Ngwathelana Hlogwana ya Tsie*” that everyone should have something to eat, despite their size. This means that this practice deprives others of having a piece of head of the locust (employment), especially graduates. This paper also found solid and sound conundrums associated with individuals holding multiple jobs in South Africa. This conundrum includes perpetual high unemployment, high concentration of experience on one person, inequitable distribution of resources, undermining of trust and inefficient management. The way to address this challenge is to establish a way to prohibit individuals from holding multiple jobs in the country. From the above discussion, it is clear that individuals holding multiple job opportunities create a barrier for graduates to secure employment in South Africa. This means that there is monopolisation of job opportunities in the country because young graduates without sufficient experience cannot secure entry-level jobs.

Recommendations and Conclusion

The study therefore concludes that people holding several job opportunities maintain graduate unemployment in the Republic of South Africa, regardless of the years of the private bodies and the South African government fighting to lower graduate unemployment. The study suggests that novel graduate unemployment has played a part in the worsening of poverty in South Africa. Thus, the study suggests that there is a need to set up a legal framework that restricts the number of positions that can be held in South Africa. In addition, the study further deduces that initiating mentorship programs where inexperienced labourers are teamed up with experts/old hands. Additionally, instituting public awareness campaigns to upskill both the workman and the bossman about the negative outcomes of holding several job positions, and the interest of fair employment practice, and motivating Civil Society Organizations (CSO) and labour unions to champion for policy changes that tackle these concerns at the national level, driving for

reforms that promote equitable employment practices and lower unemployment. As a result, the paper aimed to investigate the impact of individuals holding multiple jobs on graduate unemployment in South Africa.

Study's Contribution

The study put forward important contributions in the discussion on graduate unemployment in South Africa, specifically in connection to the execution of people holding several job positions. In addition, its high point is an undebated factor adding to the high rates of graduate unemployment in the country. For example, the centralization of job opportunities amongst a select group of people who occupy several positions. As a result, the study uses the Sepedi proverb “*Bana Ba Motho Ba Ngwathelana Hlogwana Ya Tsie*” through which this study spotlights the significance of equitable employment distribution and shows practical value. Thus, the study recommends the formation of a legal framework to curb the number of positions that an individual can occupy in the formal private and public sectors. Therefore, the paper aimed to investigate the impact of individuals holding multiple jobs on graduate unemployment in South Africa.

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